

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF FORMING ECOLOGICAL CONCEPTS IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES TO PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. In this article, the development of an excellent system of environmental education and its introduction into the educational system, the reduction of anthropogenic damage to nature, the main principles of environmental education, the improvement of elementary school students' understanding of ecology based on a creative approach, the main focus is on the environment. - Issues such as environmental protection, rational and economical use of nature will be discussed.

Keywords: lesson, student, environmental policy, nature, society, cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

It is necessary to develop an excellent system of ecological education and introduce it into the educational system. The earlier environmental education starts, that is, from the primary school age, the more positive and effective it will be. In the family, society, educational institutions and other areas, it is necessary to continuously form ecological thinking, ecological awareness and ecological culture. The time demands that the effective teaching of natural sciences to students in primary grades should be established as an ecological foundation [2].

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

For this, every primary school teacher should first of all be able to inculcate

the concepts of ecological thinking, ecological education and ecological culture in the young students. For this, the cooperation of biologists, geographers, geologists, and meteorologists in reducing anthropogenic damage to nature is very necessary. The main basis of environmental education is to convey the essence of these relations to the minds of young students, to teach them to be able to properly implement their relationship with nature. The scientific basis of ecological knowledge is explained in the process of theoretical, practical knowledge and independent work [3].

RESULTS

Indeed, President Sh.M. As Mirziyoyev noted, the fact that our youth are able to rightfully take responsibility for the future of our country, and that they are becoming the decisive force of our today and tomorrow, gives us all pride. It is necessary to bring our large-scale work in this field to a logical end, in particular, our adopted nationwide programs on education [1].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The lesson is an important tool for improving elementary school students' understanding of ecology based on a creative approach. Because students form their scientific worldview to a certain extent while studying academic subjects. In this process, the teacher achieves the level of effectiveness of the lesson through the harmony of his thinking and activity. The teacher uses a variety of methods and techniques in the systematic presentation of the educational material, taking into account the theoretical knowledge, practical skills, qualifications and competencies of the students [4].

Also, the main focus on improving elementary school students' understanding of ecology based on a creative approach is global knowledge related to environmental protection, rational and economical use of nature, and the use of technologies aimed at improving the environment. is to have.

Today, attention is being paid to issues related to sustainable development,

knowledge of global and regional environmental problems. At the same time, one of the main sources of ecological concepts is the spiritual values of the Uzbek people, the values related to the preservation of nature, environment and cultural heritage, which are related to protection, preservation, reproduction and transmission to the next generation. qualities such as personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, determination, and initiative are formed and improved.

Today, environmental problems are often caused by ignorance of environmental laws and non-compliance with them. For this reason, the preservation of a healthy natural environment largely depends on the level of students' awareness of environmental legislation and their practical compliance [5].

Educational activities outside the classroom are also important in organizing creative activities in the formation of concepts related to ecology among elementary school students, and its main feature is to prepare students for social life. As a continuation of their daily work, students directly participate in conversations and question-and-answer sessions of various content in educational activities outside the classroom, participate in organizing parties, create wall newspapers, play roles, listen, etc., thereby enriching their knowledge and spiritual world [6].

Researchers in each field of science use different methods to study the object in the course of their research. The analysis of the literature showed that environmental education and nature protection were interpreted differently in different periods. Because the impact of human activity on nature and the need for nature protection, the historical foundations of environmental education are reflected in the development of human society.

Today, great attention is being paid to issues of ecological education, ecological thinking, and ecological culture. It is in primary classes that

environmental education is regularly improved during lessons and extracurriculars. That is, during extracurricular time, students are taken to the heart of nature, to nature museums, and the formation of elements of environmental education in the process of Saturdays, conversations, mornings is the basis of our opinion. In addition, for the purpose of providing ecological education, the inclusion of creative content of ecological knowledge in new generation textbooks will certainly serve to increase the level of environmental knowledge of students.

CONCLUSIONS

Parents should react to students' negative attitude towards the environment and explain the negative consequences of this, and earnestly encourage them to ensure the cleanliness of the natural environment, the purity of the air, and above all, our health and the stability of our lives. It is necessary to transform the rule of "a clean environment is a healthy life environment" into a family's lifestyle and worldview, daily necessities, practical skills and vital needs.

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